

FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH CHRONIC DISEASE ADHERENCE AND DELAY IN PRESENTATION TO A RHEUMATOLOGIST AMONG PATIENTS ATTENDING A RHEUMATOLOGY OUTPATIENT CLINIC

Keywords

Chronic disease adherence,

Treatment adherence,

Rheumatic diseases,

Delay in rheumatology consultation

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ABSTRACT

Treatment adherence and timely access to specialist care are essential in rheumatic disease management and may be influenced by sociodemographic and healthcare-related factors. To evaluate treatment adherence in adult patients with rheumatic diseases and its association with sociodemographic characteristics, comorbidities, use of traditional treatments, and delay in rheumatology consultation. This descriptive cross-sectional study included adult patients with rheumatic diseases. Treatment adherence and time from symptom onset to first rheumatology consultation were assessed. Sociodemographic, clinical, and healthcare access-related variables were analyzed. The mean age was 46 years, and 67.9% were female. The median time to rheumatology consultation was 180 days. Lower adherence was observed among men, older individuals, those with lower education levels, unemployed patients, and those with comorbidities. Higher adherence was associated with employment, higher education, and absence of comorbidities. Earlier consultation was linked to better adherence. Use of traditional treatment methods was also associated with higher adherence. Delays were common and often related to processes in other specialties. Treatment adherence is influenced by sociodemographic factors and healthcare access. Early rheumatology consultation and effective referral systems may improve adherence in patients with rheumatic diseases.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines chronic diseases as conditions that typically last longer than three months, significantly limit an individual's daily activities and functional capacity, and require long-term management¹. A wide range of conditions fall within this category, including cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, respiratory diseases, cancers, neurological disorders, kidney diseases, and rheumatic diseases².

Rheumatic diseases represent a heterogeneous group of disorders primarily affecting the musculoskeletal system, including joints, bones, muscles, and connective tissues³. According to global data, the prevalence of rheumatic diseases ranges between 9.8% and 33.2%⁴. The frequency of rheumatologic manifestations increases with age. Functional impairment, one of the most common clinical manifestations, is observed in approximately 3.1% of individuals under the age of 60, whereas this rate rises to nearly 50% among those aged 75 years and older⁵.

Treatment adherence is defined as the extent to which patients follow physicians' recommendations and use prescribed medications as directed⁶. Patients and physicians should establish a shared understanding of key components of treatment, including duration, dosage, and frequency of medication use. Adequate patient education regarding treatment options constitutes a critical step in achieving this shared understanding⁷. However, factors such as age-related cognitive decline, physical limitations, socioeconomic constraints, polypharmacy, and complex treatment regimens may negatively affect adherence, particularly in older populations^{8,9}.

In rheumatology, adherence to treatment is of particular importance, as these conditions often require long-term or lifelong management. Poor adherence may lead to disease progression and worse clinical outcomes¹⁰. Another important factor influencing treatment adherence is the availability of sufficient healthcare personnel to provide adequate care. In the field of rheumatology, workforce shortages remain a significant challenge. Despite the increasing number of patients, the

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number of rheumatologists may be insufficient to meet demand. Strengthening the rheumatology workforce is essential to improve timely access to diagnosis, evaluation, and treatment¹¹.

This issue directly affects the time interval between symptom onset and the first consultation with a rheumatology specialist. Prolonged delays in accessing specialist care may result in delayed diagnosis and treatment initiation. Previous studies have identified several contributing factors to delayed access, including insufficient numbers of rheumatologists, difficulties in obtaining appointments, delays in primary healthcare services, and prolonged diagnostic processes¹²⁻¹⁴.

Although previous studies have examined factors influencing treatment adherence in rheumatic diseases, integrated evaluations of adherence and healthcare access remain limited. Differences in patient profiles, access to services, and availability of specialists may also lead to variability between centers. Therefore, data from a center serving a large and diverse patient population may contribute to the literature.

This study aimed to evaluate treatment adherence among adult patients with rheumatic diseases and its association with sociodemographic characteristics, comorbidities, use of traditional treatment methods, and delay in rheumatology consultation. It also sought to identify factors contributing to delayed access to rheumatology care.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in 2023 among adult patients (≥ 18 years) presenting to the Rheumatology Outpatient Clinic of Sivas Cumhuriyet University Hospital. A total of 131 participants were included. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of sociodemographic and disease-related variables, along with the Chronic Disease Adherence Scale, which includes physical, social, and psychological subdimensions. Higher scores indicate better adherence.

The main outcomes were treatment adherence and the time from symptom onset to first rheumatology consultation. The latter was calculated based on patient self-report and dichotomized according to the median value.

Independent variables included age, gender, marital status, employment status, educational level, income–expenditure status, social security, presence of comorbid chronic disease, use of traditional treatment methods, healthcare utilization patterns, referral source, and number of medications.

Reasons for delay in rheumatology consultation were categorized as delays related to diagnostic and treatment processes in other specialties or other factors such as access and transportation barriers.

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 22.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation or median values, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Student's t-test or Mann–Whitney U test was used as appropriate, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 154 patients who presented to the rheumatology outpatient clinic between January 1, 2023, and May 4, 2023, and agreed to complete the questionnaire were initially included in the study. After excluding incomplete or incorrectly completed questionnaires, the final study group consisted of 131 patients.

As shown in Table 1, the mean age of the study population was 46.59 ± 14.65 years. Females constituted the majority of the participants (67.9%, $n = 89$). Similarly, 67.9% ($n = 89$) of the participants were married. More than half of the study group were unemployed (54.2%, $n = 71$).

In terms of educational status, the proportion of individuals who were illiterate or primary school graduates was higher (51.1%, $n = 67$) compared to those with higher education levels. Regarding household income, 57.3% ($n = 75$) of the participants reported that their income was equal to or greater than their expenses.

The vast majority of participants had health insurance coverage (93.1%, $n = 122$) (Table 1).

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of the study population

Continuos Variables	Mean \pm Std Dev.	Min-Max
Age (Years)	46.59 \pm 14.65	19-78
Categorical Variables	n	%
Gender		
Female	89	67.9
Male	42	32.1
Marital Status		
Single	42	32.1
Married	89	67.9
Employment Status		
Not working/Retired	71	54.2
Working	60	45.8
Educational Level		
Illiterate/Primary school	67	51.1
High school and above	64	48.9
Income Status		
Income less than expenses	56	42.7
Income equal to or greater than expenses	75	57.3
Health Insurance		
Yes	122	93.1
No	9	6.9

The median duration between symptom onset and the first consultation with a rheumatology specialist was 180 days. In the study group, 42.7% (n = 56) of the participants had an additional chronic disease other than their rheumatologic condition. Among these, hypertension was the most common comorbidity (n = 15). The majority of participants (66.4%, n = 87) reported not using traditional treatment methods. Among the 44 patients who used such methods, 28 had undergone cupping therapy (hijama).

Prior to consultation with a rheumatologist, 44.3% (n = 58) of the patients had been examined by an internal medicine specialist. Furthermore, 71.8% (n = 94) were referred to a rheumatologist by another physician. A total of 59.5% (n = 78) of participants reported that the delay between symptom onset and the first rheumatology consultation was mainly due to diagnostic and treatment processes carried out by physicians from other specialties.

The most frequently observed diagnoses in the study group were rheumatoid arthritis (24.4%, n = 32) and ankylosing spondylitis (16.0%, n = 21). More than half of the participants (50.4%, n = 66) were examined by a rheumatologist approximately 150 days after the onset of their symptoms (Table 2).

The mean scores of the study group were 38.40 \pm 7.60 for the physical subdimension, 22.90 \pm 5.10 for the social subdimension, 27.60 \pm 4.80 for the psychological subdimension, and 88.60 \pm 12.40 for the total adherence score. When the relationship between gender and adherence to chronic disease was examined, males had significantly lower physical, psychological, and total adherence scores compared to females ($p < 0.001$, $p = 0.003$, and $p = 0.025$, respectively).

Participants aged ≥ 60 years had significantly lower social, psychological, and total adherence scores compared to those aged < 60 years ($p < 0.001$, $p = 0.014$, and $p = 0.007$, respectively). No statistically significant association was found between adherence scores and marital status or income level.

Employed participants had significantly higher social adherence scores compared to those who were not working ($p = 0.002$). Participants with a high school or higher level of education had significantly higher social and total adherence scores compared to those who were illiterate or had only primary education ($p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.002$, respectively).

Individuals without an additional chronic disease had significantly higher social and total adherence scores compared to those with comorbid chronic conditions ($p = 0.002$ and $p = 0.040$, respectively). Participants who reported using traditional

treatment methods had significantly higher social, psychological, and total adherence scores compared to those who did not use such methods ($p = 0.019$, $p = 0.022$, and $p = 0.046$, respectively). Patients who were examined by a rheumatologist within 150 days of symptom onset had significantly higher physical and total adherence scores compared to those who had a later consultation ($p = 0.006$ for both comparisons) (Table 3).

Table 2. Disease-related characteristics of the study population

Continuous Variables	Median	(Q 25-75)
Time to first rheumatology consultation (days)	180.00	(30-1000)
Categorical Variables	n	%
Comorbid chronic diseases (n = 56)		
Hypertension	15	26.8
Diabetes mellitus	13	23.2
Other (colitis, asthma, goiter, cardiovascular diseases)	28	50.0
Use of traditional treatment methods		
Yes	44	33.6
No	87	66.4
Most commonly used traditional methods (n = 44)		
Cupping therapy (hijama)	28	63.6
Leech therapy	11	25.0
Multiple methods	5	11.4
Physicians consulted prior to rheumatology visit		
Family physician	3	2.3
Internal medicine specialist	58	44.3
Physical therapy and rehabilitation specialist	33	25.2
Orthopedics specialist	8	6.1
Other single specialties	3	2.3
Multiple specialties	26	19.8
Referral source to rheumatologist		
Physician	94	71.8
Others (neighbors/internet)	37	28.2
Reason for delay in first rheumatology consultation		
Delays due to diagnostic/treatment processes in other specialties	78	59.5
Other reasons (e.g., lack of appointments)	53	40.5
Most common diagnoses		
Rheumatoid arthritis	32	24.4
Ankylosing spondylitis	21	16.0
Familial Mediterranean fever	20	15.3
Behçet's disease	10	7.6
Systemic lupus erythematosus	6	4.6
Sjögren's syndrome	6	4.6
Connective tissue diseases	7	5.3
Fibromyalgia	15	11.5
Other	4	3.1
Multiple diagnoses	10	7.6
Time to first consultation (days)		
0-150	65	49.6
≥151	66	50.4

DISCUSSION

In this study, adherence to chronic disease treatment among patients presenting to a rheumatology outpatient clinic was found to vary according to sociodemographic and clinical

characteristics. Lower adherence scores were observed among males, individuals aged 60 years and older, those with lower educational levels, unemployed participants, and patients with comorbid chronic conditions, with these associations reaching statistical significance.

In contrast, patients who were evaluated by a rheumatology proportion of participants attributed delays in accessing specialist at an earlier stage demonstrated significantly higher rheumatology care to prolonged diagnostic and treatment physical and total adherence scores. Additionally, a substantial processes in other medical specialties.

Table 3. Chronic Disease Adherence Scale scores according to sociodemographic and disease-related characteristics

Variables	Physical Mean ± SD	Social Mean ± SD	Psychological Mean ± SD	Total Mean ± SD
N=131	38.40±7.60	22.90 ± 5.10	27.60 ± 4.80	88.60 ± 12.40
Gender				
Female (n=89)	39.52 ± 7.03	21.51 ± 4.58	27.66 ± 3.55	88.70 ± 11.5
Male (n=42)	34.80 ± 7.54	22.85 ± 4.54	25.60 ± 3.91	83.66 ±12.25
P[*]	<0.001	0.120	0.003	0.025
Age				
≤59 (n=102)	37.99±6.69	23.03±3.61	27.44±3.55	88.68±10.43
≥60 (n=29)	38.10±9.99	18.06±5.54	25.44±4.21	81.62±15.22
P^{**}	0.553	<0.001	0.014	0.007
Marital status				
Single (n=42)	37.66±6.93	21.76±3.96	27.21±3.43	86.64±10.74
Married (n=89)	38.17±7.78	22.01±4.88	26.89±3.94	87.32
P[*]	0.716	0.773	0.658	0.761
Employment Status				
Not working/Retired (n=71)	38.42±7.54	20.83±4.89	27.16±4.13	86.42±12.49
Working (n=60)	37.53±7.48	23.25±3.84	26.80±3.34	87.93±11.37
P[*]	0.501	0.002	0.580	0.476
Educational Level				
Low (n=67)	37.13±7.56	20.17±4.52	26.73±3.79	84.04±11.51
High (n=64)	38.93±7.38	23.79±3.90	27.28±3.77	90.36±11.67
P[*]	0.170	<0.001	0.408	0.002
Income Status				
Low (n=56)	37.67±8.35	21.66±4.50	26.71±4.27	86.05±13.51
Equal/Higher (n=75)	38.26±6.84	22.13±4.68	27.21±3.38	87.90±10.63
P[*]	0.659	0.562	0.457	0.385
Comorbid Chronic Disease				
No (n=74)	38.52±7.05	23.01±4.16	27.17±3.58	89.01±11.37
Yes (n=57)	37.35±8.06	20.54±4.78	26.77±4.04	84.66±12.38
P[*]	0.376	0.002	0.547	0.040
Use of Traditional Methods				
No (n=85)	38.35±7.83	21.24±4.92	26.44±3.83	85.72±13.03
Yes (n=46)	37.97±6.93	23.22±3.59	28.02±3.49	89.71±9.25
P[*]	0.967	0.019	0.022	0.046
Time to Consultation (days)				
0-150 (n=65)	39.81±7.41	22.67±4.75	27.46±3.84	89.95±12.57
≥151 (n=66)	36.24±7.21	21.18±4.33	26.54±3.69	84.26±10.70
P[*]	0.006	0.064	0.167	0.006

These findings suggest that adherence to chronic disease management is influenced not only by individual-level factors but also by broader determinants related to healthcare access and the organization of care pathways.

The relationship between sociodemographic characteristics and treatment adherence has been widely emphasized in the literature. Previous studies investigating adherence among patients with rheumatic and other chronic diseases have reported that factors such as educational level, age, economic status, and employment status significantly influence treatment adherence. In particular, lower educational attainment and advanced age have been associated with difficulties in understanding the treatment process and adhering to prescribed therapeutic regimens^{10,15}.

Similarly, a study examining self-efficacy in chronic diseases demonstrated that higher levels of education and income, receiving disease-related education, and the presence of health insurance were associated with increased self-efficacy¹⁶. Consistent with these findings, the results of the present study highlight the important role of socioeconomic factors in chronic disease management. These findings suggest that targeted interventions are needed to improve treatment adherence among individuals with lower educational levels, older age groups, and disadvantaged socioeconomic status.

Given the heterogeneous nature of rheumatic diseases, it is well established that sociodemographic characteristics may vary across different disease subtypes. A study evaluating medication adherence in patients with rheumatoid arthritis and ankylosing spondylitis reported a predominance of females among rheumatoid arthritis patients and males among ankylosing spondylitis patients, with both conditions occurring more frequently in individuals under the age of 60. In addition, rheumatic diseases have been reported to be more prevalent among individuals with lower educational levels, and employment status may vary across different disease groups¹⁷. In the present study, the predominance of rheumatoid arthritis among participants, along with the observed associations between adherence and advanced age, lower educational level, and unemployment, appears to be consistent with the general trends reported in the literature.

The presence of comorbid chronic diseases represents another important factor in the management of chronic conditions. The

literature indicates that comorbidities can complicate treatment processes and may negatively affect adherence. The need to implement multiple treatment regimens for different conditions, an increased number of medications, and overlapping symptoms can make disease management more challenging⁹.

In the present study, higher social and total adherence scores among individuals without additional chronic diseases suggest that less complex treatment processes may facilitate better adherence. Furthermore, the high prevalence of hypertension and diabetes among comorbid conditions in our study highlights the substantial burden of chronic diseases and their potential impact on the management of rheumatic conditions.

Delays between symptom onset and evaluation by a rheumatology specialist are frequently emphasized in the literature as a significant barrier to early diagnosis and timely treatment in rheumatic diseases. In this study, the median duration between symptom onset and the first rheumatology consultation was found to be 180 days, and more than half of the participants were evaluated approximately 150 days after symptom onset.

Moreover, 59.5% of participants attributed the delay in accessing rheumatology care to diagnostic and treatment processes carried out in other medical specialties. It was also observed that, prior to consulting a rheumatologist, patients most commonly presented to internal medicine specialists (44.3%), and the majority (71.8%) were referred to a rheumatologist by another physician.

These findings suggest that evaluation and referral processes across different medical specialties may prolong the time required to access rheumatology care, potentially delaying appropriate diagnosis and treatment in patients with rheumatic diseases.

Consistent with our findings, delays in accessing rheumatology care have been widely reported in the literature. In a study including 822 patients with rheumatoid arthritis, the median duration between symptom onset and consultation with a rheumatology specialist was reported to be 27.2 weeks, and only 20% of patients were able to access a rheumatologist within the first three months after symptom onset. The same study also indicated that patients consulted family physicians or other healthcare providers an average of four times before

being referred to a rheumatologist. These findings suggest that repeated consultations in non-rheumatology specialties and referral pathways may significantly prolong the time to specialist care.

In line with this evidence, a considerable proportion of patients in our study had consulted multiple specialties prior to rheumatology referral and attributed delays to these processes, supporting previously reported patterns¹⁷.

Similarly, a multicenter study conducted across eight European centers reported a median delay of 24 weeks between symptom onset and rheumatology evaluation in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. In that study, only 8–42% of patients were assessed by a rheumatologist within the first 12 weeks following symptom onset. Importantly, the study demonstrated that delays are not solely related to patient behavior but rather reflect a complex, multi-step process involving healthcare professionals and systemic factors.

Our findings are consistent with this multi-level delay model, as a substantial proportion of patients experienced delayed access to rheumatology care and associated these delays with diagnostic and treatment processes in other medical specialties¹⁸.

In another study examining referral processes to rheumatology care, it was reported that 40% of patients were referred within the first month, 24% waited between one and three months, and 36% were referred after four months or longer. The study emphasized that one of the main causes of diagnostic delay was delayed referral from primary care or other medical specialties.

Consistent with these findings, the majority of patients in our study were referred to a rheumatologist by another physician, and a substantial proportion attributed delays in accessing specialist care to evaluation processes in other medical fields, supporting the evidence reported in the literature¹⁹.

Similarly, a cohort study conducted among patients with ankylosing spondylitis reported that the median duration between the initial diagnosis of back pain and referral to a rheumatologist was 307 days (approximately 10 months). In that study, patients most frequently consulted family physicians, orthopedics, physical medicine and rehabilitation,

and pain clinics prior to rheumatology referral.

In our study, the presence of multiple prior consultations in different specialties particularly the prominent role of internal medicine suggests that early recognition of rheumatic diseases may be challenging. This, in turn, may lead to prolonged evaluation processes across different specialties before appropriate referral to rheumatology care is achieved²⁰.

Some studies have reported that the duration between symptom onset and referral to a rheumatology specialist in patients with rheumatoid arthritis can extend up to 17 months. This finding highlights that diagnostic delay in rheumatic diseases represents a significant clinical problem that may arise at multiple levels of the healthcare system²¹.

In the present study, the median time to rheumatology consultation was 180 days, which is consistent with the delay periods reported in the literature. These findings further emphasize the importance of early diagnosis and the development of effective referral mechanisms in the management of rheumatic diseases.

Complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) practices have increasingly been used in the management of chronic diseases. The World Health Organization defines these practices as health-related approaches rooted in cultural beliefs and traditions, often transmitted across generations^{22,23}. The prevalence of CAM use varies across countries, and in Türkiye, its utilization has increased in recent years, particularly following regulatory developments²⁴.

In chronic diseases, CAM methods are commonly used to alleviate symptoms, reduce pain, and improve quality of life (25). In our study, individuals who reported using traditional treatment methods demonstrated significantly higher social, psychological, and total adherence scores. This finding may suggest that these individuals adopt a more active approach in coping with their disease.

However, this association should not be interpreted as a direct causal effect of traditional methods on treatment adherence. Rather, it should be considered within the broader context of patients' health behaviors, social support systems, and individual disease experiences.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, adherence to chronic disease treatment among patients attending a rheumatology outpatient clinic is influenced by both sociodemographic factors and healthcare access-related variables. Male gender, older age, lower educational level, unemployment, and comorbidities were associated with lower adherence, whereas earlier consultation with a rheumatologist was linked to better adherence. These findings highlight the importance of early recognition, timely referral, and targeted patient education, particularly for high-risk groups. While the study's comprehensive approach and diverse patient population are strengths, its cross-sectional and single-center design limit causal inference and generalizability. Further multicenter, prospective studies are warranted.

Conflicts of Interest Statement

There are no potential conflicts of interest.

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No

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